

EXPLORING ROCKET PROPELLANTS AND THEIR TYPES

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Annotation: The main purpose of studying this topic is to determine what kind of fuel and their types are used by carrier rockets flying into space with various tasks. To study the types of fuels and in what situations they are actively used. Evaluation of the efficiency of combined fuels. And exploring why combined fuels are useful for the financial performance of the company.

Key words: Solid propellants, liquid-fueled system, liquid hydrogen, hybrid propellant, compressed gases.

Introduction: Rocket propellant serves as the reaction mass ejected to generate thrust, with energy derived from either the propellants, as in chemical rockets, or from an external source, like in ion engines. While chemical rockets rely on exothermic reactions to produce high-pressure gases, ion engines utilize electric power to accelerate ions, offering higher efficiency but lower thrust. Each type of propulsion system has distinct advantages and applications, influencing spacecraft design and mission profiles.

Rockets generate thrust by expelling mass rearward at high velocity, with thrust calculated by multiplying the mass flow rate of the propellants by their exhaust velocity, known as specific impulse. Unlike airplanes that rely on pushing against air, rockets are propelled by the pressure of combusting gases acting on the combustion chamber and nozzle. This design allows rocket engines to operate more efficiently in outer space, where the absence of air pressure reduces drag and enables longer nozzles

without flow separation, maximizing thrust performance. Chemical propellants primarily release energy through redox reactions, specifically combustion, requiring both a fuel (reducing agent) and an oxidizer,[1]. In monopropellant rockets, energy can be released through the decomposition of unstable compounds like peroxides. In bipropellant liquid rockets, fuels and oxidizers are combined in a combustion chamber, often with a turbopump to manage pressure, converting liquid propellant into a vast volume of high-temperature gases. This gas is expelled through the engine nozzle at high velocity, generating thrust in accordance with Newton's laws of motion and propelling the rocket forward.

Solid rocket propellant originated in the 13th century during the Chinese Song dynasty, with the introduction of gunpowder in 1232. By the 1950s and 60s, U.S. researchers developed ammonium perchlorate composite propellant (APCP), which comprises 69-70% ammonium perchlorate as an oxidizer, 16-20% aluminum powder as fuel, and 11-14% polybutadiene rubber as a binder, forming a flexible solid after casting and curing. Although the use of APCP is historically limited, it serves as a foundation for military applications, which utilize various solid propellants that can outperform APCP. In the 1970s and 80s, the U.S. fully transitioned to solid-fueled intercontinental ballistic missiles (ICBMs) like the LGM-30 Minuteman, while the USSR/Russia adopted similar solid-fueled systems, retaining some liquid-fueled ICBMs. Both sides' solid-fueled ICBMs typically featured three initial solid stages and utilized precision maneuverable buses for trajectory adjustments of their warheads,[2].

Methodolgy: Solid propellants are classified into two main types: composites and single/double/triple bases. Composites consist of a mixture of granules of solid oxidizers, such as ammonium nitrate, with flakes or powders of energetic fuel compounds, like RDX or HMX, along with additives like polymer binding agents, plasticizers, and burn rate modifiers. Single-, double-, or triple-bases are homogeneous mixtures of one to three primary ingredients, which must include fuel and oxidizer, and often binders and plasticizers,[3]. These ingredients can have multiple roles, with

examples including RDX being both a fuel and oxidizer, and nitrocellulose serving as a fuel, oxidizer, and structural polymer.

Liquid-fueled rockets offer significant advantages over solid rockets, including higher specific impulse and the ability to be throttled, shut down, and restarted. In a **liquid-fueled system**, only the combustion chamber must endure high pressures and temperatures, allowing for regenerative cooling using the liquid propellant. With systems utilizing turbopumps, the propellant tanks can be maintained at a lower pressure than the combustion chamber, which reduces the overall mass of the tanks.. These benefits contribute to the preference for liquid propellants in most orbital launch vehicles.

The theoretical exhaust velocity of a rocket propellant is directly linked to its specific energy, with unburned fuel or oxidizers leading to energy loss and reduced specific energy. Many rockets operate fuel-rich mixtures, which lower theoretical exhaust velocities but produce lighter exhaust species, enhancing performance. The rocket nozzle plays a crucial role in converting thermal energy from the combustion of propellants into directed kinetic energy, such as CO and H₂, have fewer vibrational and rotational energy modes compared to larger energy as the propellants exit the engine in approximately one millisecond. Smaller molecules like CO₂ and H₂O, leading to more of the thermal energy being available for translation and subsequent conversion into kinetic energy. As a result, running rich mixtures improves nozzle efficiency, allowing real rocket engines to achieve higher actual exhaust velocities despite lower theoretical ones.

Liquid hydrogen offers a high specific impulse (I_{sp}) but poses challenges due to its low density, requiring larger tanks and components that increase dry mass and operational complexities, making it expensive to handle. Despite these drawbacks, liquid hydrogen is ideal for upper stages where I_{sp} is crucial and thrust-to-weight ratios are less critical. In contrast, vehicles using dense propellants may have lower I_{sp} but benefit from a higher takeoff thrust due to smaller engine components, allowing them to achieve orbit more efficiently by minimizing gravity losses. The tripropellant rocket

concept addresses these issues by utilizing dense fuel at low altitudes and switching to hydrogen at higher elevations,[4]. The Space Shuttle exemplified this approach, relying on dense solid rocket boosters for initial thrust while its main engines operated on a hydrogen-oxygen mixture to maximize efficiency during the latter stages of ascent once the boosters were jettisoned.

Hybrid propellant rockets combine the advantages of solid and liquid fuels by utilizing a solid fuel with a storable oxidizer, typically in liquid form, which allows for higher specific impulse (I_{sp}) while maintaining the simplicity of solid rockets. This design enables features such as throttling and restarting the engine, similar to liquid rockets. Hybrids can also offer improved environmental safety compared to traditional solid rockets, as they often use less toxic oxidizers like liquid oxygen or nitrous oxide instead of hazardous materials like ammonium perchlorate, although care must be taken as some hybrid systems do incorporate harmful substances. Their configuration, where one propellant is solid and the other is fluid, can lead to simpler design requirements with fewer components such as piping, valves, and pumps, streamlining the overall system while still providing effective propulsion.

Thermal rockets utilize inert propellants with low molecular weights that can withstand high temperatures, with solar thermal and nuclear thermal variants primarily using liquid hydrogen for an impressive specific impulse (I_{sp}) ranging from 600 to 900 seconds, or water vapor for about 190 seconds. Nuclear thermal rockets generate energy by harnessing the heat produced from nuclear fission, and some designs isolate the nuclear fuel from the working fluid to reduce the risk of radioactive contamination; however, challenges with nuclear fuel loss have been notable in testing. In contrast, solar thermal rockets rely on concentrated sunlight to heat the propellant, eliminating the need for a nuclear reactor while still aiming for efficient propulsion. Both types of thermal rockets offer distinct advantages in terms of efficiency and operational mechanisms, making them promising options for advanced space missions.

For low-performance applications like attitude control jets, **compressed gases** such as nitrogen are used, storing energy through pressurized inert gas. Despite this,

the low density of gases and the substantial mass of the pressure vessels required for containment limit their practical use in modern propulsion systems,[5]. As a result, while compressed gases can be effective for specific small-scale functions, their overall utility in propulsion is constrained by these significant drawbacks, leading to a preference for more efficient and compact alternatives in many applications.

Conclusion: To sum up, the types of fuel studied in this topic are actively used today. Each propellant has its own function, as mentioned above, because they contribute a lot to achieving advanced goals in space. Back in the past, we have made great strides in discovering new rocket propellants over the course of a century. The propellants used for rockets today contribute significantly to the low cost of utilizing of rockets in space. Examples of this are compressed gas and hybrid propellants.

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